

Sodium orthovanadate solution, to which required quantity of hydrochloric acid was added in the ratio¹ 1:1, 1:2 and 1:2.4 to have theoretically the corresponding poly-vanadate ion in solution, was taken in the cell. In conductometric and potentiometric titrations addition of ethanol to the extent of 10% of the solution in the cell made the end point sharper. Samarium nitrate solution was added from a microburette in regularly increasing instalments.

In analytical method the composition of the precipitated vanadate was found by subtracting the quantity of samarium and vanadium estimated in the supernatant liquid from that present in the solution used.

The results obtained from the above experiments are tabulated in Table I.

Four different vanadates of samarium (III) can be obtained by the interaction between samarium nitrate and sodium ortho-vanadate solution containing varying quantity of hydrochloric acid.

(i) When no acid is added and pH is above 9;

(ii) When $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$ ratio is equal to 1:1 and the pH of the solution is about 7.6;

(iii) When $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$ ratio is equal to 1:2 and pH of the vanadate solution is about 6.3;

(iv) When $(\text{VO}_4)^{3-} : \text{H}^+$ ratio is equal to 1:2.4 and pH of the solution about 5.3;

Compound like $\text{Ca}_3\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28} \cdot 16\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ag}_6\text{V}_{10}\text{O}_{28}$ have been reported earlier by Rossotti⁷ and Shivahare⁸.

On further acidification vanadyl cation, VO_2^+ is formed.

References

1. G. C. SHIVAHARE and N. D. JOSHI, *Zhur. neorg. Khim.*, 1969, **14**, 603.
2. H. J. EMELEUS and J. S. ANDERSON, *Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry*, 3rd Ed. Routledge and Kegan, London, 1960, p. 324.
3. P. T. CLEVE, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1885, **43**, 162.
4. I. M. KOLTHOFF and E. B. SANDELL, *Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, 3rd Ed., MacMillan Co., New York, 1952, p. 693.
5. L. CECIL WILSON and W. DAVIED WILSON, *Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry*. Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1962, Vol. **10**, p. 460.
6. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. ELVING PHILIP. *Treatise on Analytical Chemistry*, Part II, Inter Science Publishers, 1963, p. 56.
7. F. J. C. ROSSOTTI and H. ROSSOTTI, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1956, **10**, 957.
8. G. C. SHIVAHARE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 1881.

Stobbe Condensation with Arylidene Acetophenones

B. H. PATWARDHAN

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur

Manuscript received 13 July 1972; revised 4 November 1972;

accepted 7 June 1973

STOBBE and Russwurm¹ had reported a failure of the Stobbe condensation of benzylidene acetophenone and diethyl succinate in the presence of sodium ethoxide in ether, but it is observed that the reaction proceeds smoothly in the presence of potassium tert. butoxide, which is known to be a better catalyst² for Stobbe condensation.

Condensation of a number of substituted arylidene acetophenones (chalcones) (I) with dimethyl succinate in presence of potassium tert. butoxide in tert. butanol at room temperature under inert anhydrous conditions, gave crystalline acidic products in 40–50% yields. All these compounds showed an intense UV absorption in the region 310–350 nm with log ϵ varying from 4.0 to 4.3. On substituting phenyl by *p*-methoxyphenyl a characteristic bathochromic shift³ of about 20 nm is obtained.

Apart from the characteristic phenyl and substituted phenyl peaks⁴, all these compounds showed a characteristic diene skeleton absorption between⁵ 1604–1612 cm^{-1} . In the carbonyl absorption region all these compounds show three broad peaks/shoulders in the regions of 1710–1717 cm^{-1} , 1680–1689 cm^{-1} and 1725–1735 cm^{-1} .

These data clearly indicate structure (II) assigned for these compounds formed by the usual Stobbe mechanism⁶.

(Ar = phenyl, *p*-methoxyphenyl, 3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl, 3 : 4-dimethoxyphenyl and furyl).

Experimental

Condensation of anisylidene acetophenone with dimethyl succinate :

Anisylidene acetophenone⁷ (5 g.) and dimethyl succinate (3.5 g) were added to a solution of potassium *t*-butoxide in *t*-butanol (from 1 g. potassium in 30 ml. *t*-butanol), and mechanically stirred under inert anhydrous conditions for 45 min. The reaction mixture was acidified to congo-red with 6 *N* hydrochloric acid and the *t*-butanol was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was repeatedly extracted with ether and ether phase was extracted with ice-cold sodium carbonate solution. The alkaline layer was acidified and the resulting sticky solid was taken up in ether. Removal of solvent gave an orange material, (3.7 g.). Crystallization from solvents yielded sticky and clumped solid material, but chromatographic purification on silica-gel with petroleum ether-benzene eluant gave the crystalline solid, 3-carbomethoxy-4-phenyl-6-*p*-methoxyphenyl-hex-3,5-dienoic acid (II, Ar = *p*-methoxyphenyl), m.p. 70°-71°. Found : Eq. wt. 352, C, 71.6; H, 5.41, reqd. for C₂₁H₂₀O₆ : eq. wt. 352, C, 71.8; H, 5.45%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) = 228 (4.04), 246 (4.00), 334 (4.11). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1689, 1717 and 1734 cm⁻¹.

Similarly piperonylidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = 3 : 4-methylenedioxyphenyl), m.p. 80°-81°. (Found : eq. wt. 366, C, 69.33; H, 4.68, reqd. for C₂₁H₁₈O₆ : eq. wt. 366, C, 69.04; H, 4.66%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 244 (3.99), 290 (3.83) and 348 (3.95). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1689, 1717 and 1738 cm⁻¹. Veratralidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = 3 : 4-dimethoxyphenyl), m.p. 69°-70°. Found : eq. wt. 383, C, 69.4; H, 5.47, reqd. for C₂₂H₂₂O₆ : eq. wt. 382, C, 69.1; H, 5.75%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 230 (4.39), 336 (4.29). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1689, 1717 and 1730 cm⁻¹. Benzylidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = phenyl), m.p. 72°-73°. Found : eq.wt.

324, C, 74.7; H, 5.62, reqd. for C₂₀H₁₈O₄ : Eq. wt. 322, C, 74.52; H, 5.59%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 240 (4.15), 315 (4.27). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1695, 1710 and 1730 cm⁻¹. Furfurylidene acetophenone gave (II, Ar = furyl), m.p. 78°-79°. Found : eq. wt. 311, C, 69.6; H, 5.14, reqd. for C₁₈H₁₆O₅ : eq. wt. 312, C, 69.23; H, 5.12%. UV absorption λ_{max}^{EtOH} in nm (log ε) 248 (3.95), 365 (3.96). IR carbonyl absorption peaks 1685, 1717 and 1725 cm⁻¹.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Prof. M. V. Bhatt, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore and Prof. C. N. R. Rao, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur for the infra-red spectra and micro-analysis. He desires to express his gratitude to Dr. G. Bagavant for guidance and interest in this work and to C.S.I.R. for a junior research fellowship.

References

1. a) H. STOBBE and L. RUSSWURM, *Ann.*, 1901, **314**, 125.
b) H. STOBBE, *Ann.*, 1901, **314**, 111.
2. a) W. S. JOHNSON and G. H. DAUB, *Org. Reactions*, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1951, Vol. 6, p. 11, 68.
b) K. R. RAO and G. BAGAVANT, *Current Sci.*, 1969, **38**, 11.
3. A. I. SCOTT, *Interpretation of Ultraviolet Spectra of Natural Products*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1964, p. 109.
4. L. J. BELLAMY, *The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules*, Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1958, p. 65.
5. *Idem.*, *Ibid.*, p. 34.
6. W. S. JOHNSON, A. L. MCCLOSKEY and D. A. DUNNINGAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 514.
7. H. GILMAN and A. H. BLATT (Ed.), *Organic Synthesis*, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, *Coll. Vol. 1*, 1951, p. 79.

Complex Compounds of Diphenyl Lead-dichloride with Multidentate Schiff Bases

S. N. PODDAR & N. S. DAS

Inorganic Chemistry Department, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-32, India

Manuscript received 4 September 1972; revised 15 February 1973; accepted 11 May 1973

IN continuation of our research programme on non-transitional metal complexes of nitrogen-containing ligands¹, the investigation on the reaction of diphenyllead dihalide with some multidentate Schiff bases was undertaken.